

BIOMECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF HOCKEY PLAYERS

Khojiev Shokhrukh

Lecturer at the Uzbek State University of Physical Education and Sport

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7793923>

The biomechanical features of hockey players can have a significant impact on their athletic performance. Some of these features include high speed and agility, as well as good coordination and a deep sensitivity to changes in the environment. In addition, strength, endurance, balance, reaction speed and movement technique can also affect the performance of hockey players. Individual approach to training and development of optimal biomechanical characteristics are important aspects that help players achieve maximum performance on the ice. This article aims to explore the biomechanical characteristics of hockey players and their implications for performance enhancement.

Hockey is a multifaceted sport that requires agility and speed from players. Skating biomechanics is a fundamental aspect of hockey that affects a player's ability to move effectively on the ice. According to a study by T. Wong (2019), the ankle, knee and hip joints work in synchrony during skiing, providing efficient movement and gliding. Hockey players need to create a powerful push during the step and maintain balance during the sliding phase. The ankle joint is critical for generating a high level of force during the take-off phase and for shock absorption during the landing phase. The knee joint acts as a shock absorber during the landing phase and helps propel the body forward during the take-off phase. The hip joint contributes to forward momentum and stability during stride.

In addition to skating, hockey players also perform various moves that require strength and agility, such as checking, passing, throwing, and turning. These movements require the coordination of multiple joints and muscles to create efficient and effective movements. According to a study by K. Shea (1992), hockey players perform rotational movements, such as turns, that require the transfer of energy through the lower extremities. The hip, knee, and ankle joints are essential for stability and power generation during these movements. The torso and upper limbs are also involved in the rotational movements that players use to check, pass, and shoot.

Moreover, hockey players are at risk of injury due to collisions and high-speed impacts that occur during the game. Biomechanical factors such as joint and muscle strength, flexibility and balance have been found to influence injury risk.

According to a study by K.McKay (2019), resistance training can improve the biomechanical performance of hockey players and reduce the risk of injury. Research has shown that resistance training improves the strength and activation patterns of lower limb muscles involved in skating, resulting in more efficient and powerful movements.

In addition, the biomechanical characteristics of hockey players also influence the choice of equipment. Choosing the right equipment can increase productivity and reduce the risk of injury. According to a study by K. Karmonik (2015), the stiffness of hockey sticks affects the speed and accuracy of the throw. Research has shown that stiffer clubs produce faster, more accurate shots. Skates with the right support and fit can improve a player's balance and stability on the ice, reducing the risk of injury.

The biomechanical characteristics of hockey players is an important aspect in understanding and optimizing their physical capabilities and improving their athletic performance. Each hockey player has their own unique biomechanical features and capabilities that can affect their athletic performance. Some of these features may include:

Body Size and Composition: Hockey players can have different body sizes and muscle compositions, which can affect their strength, speed, and endurance. For example, taller players may have an advantage in achieving high speeds on the ice, but smaller players may have an advantage in maneuvering and performing technical moves.

Stick Type: Each player may have a preferred stick type, which can affect his technique and ability to control the puck. Some players may prefer stiffer sticks, which can help them hit harder, while others may prefer more flexible sticks, which allow them to control the puck more precisely.

Specialized Skills: Each hockey player may have their own specialized skills, which may include unique moves and techniques. For example, some players may be expert at coming out from behind the net or taking shots from unusual angles, while others may be more experienced at defensive moves and position control on the ice.

Physical Features: Each hockey player may have their own unique physical characteristics, which may include more developed leg muscles, better hand-eye coordination, higher stamina, etc. These features can affect a player's ability to perform certain movements and enhance their performance on the ice.

Flexibility and Mobility: Flexibility and mobility can affect a player's ability to perform technical moves and change direction on the ice.

Strength and Endurance: Strength and endurance can affect a hockey player's ability to perform more intense moves and maintain high performance throughout the game.

Balance and stability: Balance and stability can affect a player's ability to maintain position on the ice, as well as certain movements such as coming out from behind the net.

Reaction Speed: Reaction speed can affect a player's ability to respond to changes on the ice and make quick decisions.

Shot Strength: Shot strength can affect a player's ability to score goals or defend against attacking players.

Movement Technique: Each hockey player may have their own unique movement technique, which may include certain characteristics and features.

These are just a few of the biomechanical characteristics that are important to the success of ice hockey players. It is also important to develop specialized skills such as good vision and hand-eye coordination to improve the accuracy of hitting the puck. Also an important factor is the technique of movement and the use of optimal movement solutions for maximum efficiency and minimum risk of injury.

In addition, it is important to note that each hockey player has his own unique biomechanical features and abilities. Therefore, it is important to individually analyze and optimize the biomechanical characteristics of each player in order to achieve the best sports performance. This may include individual coaching, movement technique corrections, and development of individual training programs based on the specific needs of each player.

In conclusion, studying the biomechanical characteristics of hockey players helps coaches and fitness professionals create more effective training programs that maximize player performance. The unique biomechanical features of hockey players, such as high speed, agility, strength and endurance, balance and stability, reaction speed and movement technique, can have a significant impact on athletic performance. The development of individual approaches to training and the optimization of biomechanical characteristics are important aspects for achieving the maximum performance of players on the ice. Finally, 3D technologies, such as motion capture systems and virtual simulators, can significantly improve the analysis of the biomechanical characteristics of hockey players and help coaches optimize training programs. Motion capture systems accurately measure the movement of players on the ice, which makes it possible to evaluate the effectiveness of their technique and improve it. Virtual

simulators, in turn, allow players to practice their skills in a controlled environment, which can improve their reaction and decision making in real game situations and in hockey can significantly improve player performance and improve the quality of training.

References:

1. Karmonik, C., Jinguji, T. M., & Stefanovic, V. (2015). The effect of hockey stick stiffness on the performance and accuracy of wrist shots. *Journal of sports science & medicine*, 14(2), 359.
2. McKay, C. D., Tremblay, M. S., Thompson, S., & Tarnopolsky, M. (2019). Resistance training in ice hockey players: effects on body composition, muscle strength, and power. *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 33(5), 1295-1301.
3. Shea, K. G., Drezner, J. A., Potter, H. G., & LaPrade, R. F. (1992). Biomechanics of ice hockey. *Sports medicine*, 14(2), 116-135.
4. Wong, T. K., Federolf, P., Li, R. C. T., & Zhang, M. (2019). A review on ice hockey biomechanics. *Sports biomechanics*, 18(1), 1-23.
5. Karimov, A.A. The problem of training loads rationing of young hockey players at the stage of in-depth specialization in annual training cycle. *Eurasian Journal of Sport Science*, 1(2), 219-224 (2021).
6. Davletmuratov, S.R. The use of specialized exercises in the preparatory period of ice-hockey players. *Eurasian Journal of Sport Science*, 1(1), 61-64 (2021)
7. Xojijev, S.S. Yosh xokkey darvozabonlarining shaybani to'sish harakatlari samaradorligini oshirish. *Internauka*, 5 (181), 99-101 (2021).
8. Khojijev, Shokhrukh. "Problems of technical training of young hockey players." *Karakalpak Scientific Journal* 5.2 (2022): 1-7.
9. Каримов, А. Ўқув-машғулот гуруҳида ёш хоккейчиларни машғулот юкламасини оптималлаштириш. *Фан-Спортга*, (7), 39-41 (2020).
10. КАРИМОВ, А. А. (2022). Результаты педагогических наблюдений оценки физической и общей характеристики тренировочных нагрузок хоккеистов 13-14 лет. *Фан-спортга*, 28-30.
11. Давлетмуратов С.Р. Тренировочные нагрузки хоккеистов в подготовительном периоде//*Фан-спортга научно-теоритический журнал*. – Чирчик, 2020. – №4. – С. 33-35.
12. Rashidov Bakhtiyor Pulatovich. "APPLICATIONS OF STRETCHING EXERCISES TO DEVELOP THE FLEXIBILITY OF YOUNG HOCKEY PLAYERS AT THE INITIAL TRAINING STAGE". *European International Journal of*

Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies, vol. 2, no. 11, Nov. 2022,
pp. 332-5, doi:10.55640/eijmrms-02-11-72